

SOCIAL SCIENCES

„THE LIQUID PEOPLE” OF THE NEWS

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Abstract

The article analyzes the mechanisms of constituting new media schools and the semantic features of its controversial models.

The processes that accompany the introduction of innovative systems under the conditions of the new discursive media space are shown, which, in turn, determine the introduction and establishment of a pluralistic media environment in postmodern sociocultural systems.

In addition, we discuss the transformations of media discourses of the totalitarian regime in pluralistic media structures and the virtual results accompanying the implications of this reality and its transformation into imagined narratives on the border of the possible and the impossible.

Keywords: media, pluralism, simulacra, field, regime.

Introduction

The modern world lives in a situation of hypertrophied rise of information. The world is mined with informational discourses - that is, informational mines are hidden in the field of everyday life, and these mines are designed to create a kind of spectacle field of human routine existence, or, at least, to replace it and create a system of informational simulacra by the principle of surrogacy.

In such a situation, the news plays a crucial role in the phenomenological aspect of everyday life, and it completely occupies, as Sigmund Baumann calls, the existential being of the "liquid man". It is in this context that we conducted research in three universities of Georgia - media schools of Ivane Javakishvili Tbilisi State University, Shota Rustaveli Batumi State University, and Caucasus International University.

The subject of research is the methods of news representation and the strategies that turn news as a media phenomenon into a commodity-spectacle; The teaching of new media turned out to be especially difficult in post-Soviet Georgia, because Soviet media and Soviet news, as an ideological weapon, were based only on politicized information that left no room for doubt in the recipient's consciousness.

Research has shown us that this process undoubtedly left its mark, but at the same time brought the other extreme characteristic of postmodern discourse - a skeptical attitude to the reliability and authenticity of any information and the relativity of news as the status quo of information.

In such a situation, the function of the news is to be a carrier of information, not its interpreter, so that this information maintains its objectivity and quality, while at the same time not losing its attractiveness and the quality of the spectacle.

Today, the main task is to show students in the universities new media as a source of plural transmission of information, and to analyze new media discourses with them.

The **purpose of our research** is to study, on the one hand, the modern strategies and methods of teaching news in the higher educational space, and on the other hand, to determine its role in the existential daily life of the "liquid person" of the 21st century.

It is for this purpose that we observed several media schools in Georgia and those methods.

As a theoretical framework for researching the issue, we used Habermas's "theory of communicative action", because it considers the possibility of discourse in modern "liquid people" with free, equal rights.

For our research method, we chose qualitative research to the extent that it is based on the constructivist paradigm; it is also tailored to detect trends within specific groups; therefore, it is emic and based on an in-depth description of the issue. The research of focus groups led us to important results and showed that the study of news in Georgian higher educational media schools (in particular, in the three media schools studied by us) is based on modern requirements, interests and standards; For the research, we used a case analysis, a semi-structured interview (on the so-called "snow ball" principle). In order to compare media schools, we used the comparativist method.

The research showed the ontological and epistemological foundations of teaching new media in Georgia and determined the empirical nature of the issue. The work is an attempt to show how the new media developed in modern Georgia after the totalitarian regime

and what gradations it underwent; to what extent is her language today intersubjective and adapted to "liquid people". Jürgen Habermas' "theory of communication action" (1) helped us in the analysis of these processes. Author's visions helped us establish the connection between the mind and action of the modern "liquid person"; Based on the opinions of Habermas, the role of the new media in the most difficult process of shaping human rational actions was further highlighted - from a historical perspective; It became possible to understand the social actions of "liquid people" on the basis of rational criticism of knowledge; At the same time, it became easier to critically analyze the identification of progressive and regressive characteristics of modern society at the empirical level.

Hans Magnus Enzensberger's theory of Media (2) helped us a lot in working on the paper. In addition to theses of manipulation, imitation, simulation, he introduced us to the thesis of "dumbing down", which is already a solid anthropological expression. With these theses, the author claims that the media attack not only the ability of users to criticize or differ, not only their moral or political substance, but also their ability to perceive and their psychological identity. Therefore, according to Enzensberger's theory, it appeared that the new media can bring out a new person, and he, according to the scientist, can be imagined as a zombie or a mutant.

The book - "New Media A Critical Introduction" - By Martin Lister, Jon Dovey, Seth Giddings, Iain Grant, Kieran Kelly (3) showed us how to define the characteristics of new media; Its social and political role.

A collection of essays - "The New Media" by Dan Harries (4) helped us to define the influences of new media. He showed us the modern media landscape and its influences.

As a methodological basis of empirical studies, we used another book - "Competing Paradigms in Qualitative Research" by EGON G. GUBA (5); the book helped us to interpret new media discourses.

The research of the literature showed us that learning and teaching new media in Georgian media schools is an important challenge, and its innovative creative configurations are becoming more apparent day by day.

New media and its role in post-soviet Georgia

During the last 100 years, the Georgian media has gone from a totalitarian media democracy to a modern media democracy. It should be taken into account that Georgia coexisted under the Soviet regime for 70 years. Accordingly, in our political, social and mental existence, Sovietism prevailed as a way of thinking; This field was completely foreign to us. "The main idea of this field is that the state is the highest and man is nothing but a servant of the state and the state idea" (6).

Georgian media still plays a decisive role in the most difficult process of structuring civil life and consciousness.

The three Georgian media schools we studied showed how important the involvement of new media

is in this process; what role do media theorists play in creating a new type of media environment?

All three media schools - (Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University and Caucasus International University) share a fundamental principle - to "adapt" the new media paradigm to the modern "liquid person".

Students study modern media theories, get acquainted with the methods of working in the information environment and develop the skills of constituting media projects.

The study of new media occupies the most important place in all three universities; Students are helped to analyze the media space; in clarifying the processes of media evolution; The comprehensive influence of media on society and culture is also intensively studied.

Two of the universities studied by us have a modern multimedia center at the base of the media school (Ivane Javakhishvili State University and Caucasus International University), which is a necessary condition for studying new media analytics; In the near future, it is planned to establish a similar center in the media school of Shota Rustaveli University.

A multimedia center was created at Ivane Javakhishvili State University in 2016; in Caucasus International University - in 2017. These specific media schools have educational printed and online publications, radio, television, Documentary Film Studio and much more.

Therefore, on the bases of these multimedia centers, media research and multimedia production take place, which is a necessary condition for orientation in new media controversies.

The modern "liquid person" has an increased need for news. However, there is also a strong desire to receive balanced and neutral information. On the bases of media schools studied by us, students learn the dilemmas they may face in the process of work and get acquainted with several fundamental principles -

- Accuracy;
- Correcting errors (If any);
- Balance and impartiality between differing parties;
- Inadmissibility of conflict of interest;
- Determining what is of primary and secondary nature;
- Source reliability;
- Separation of the story and opinion;
- Rejection of plagiarism and fabrication;
- Using a photo or video frame/form corresponding to the content;
- Rejection of attaining information through bribery .

Understanding these fundamental principles is particularly important for the Georgian media of the post-Soviet space, because it has not yet been freed from the so-called Soviet "media complexes". Accordingly, the modern Georgian "liquid person" is

also a bearer of certain post-Soviet complexes, who has an inherent distrust of the media; The "media complex" refers to the fact that totalitarian regimes used the media to marginalize people and countries. Getting rid of this "utility" was not so easy.

There is such a Georgian proverb - "it is better to break your head than to break your name". The Georgian media is also in a "broken" state even today, in some respects, and it is difficult to get rid of the damaged Soviet image. That is why the modern "liquid person" is "distrustful" of the media even now.

The design of the research

The research design is as follows:

The place of research - - Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University; Caucasus International University (Tbilisi); Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University (Batumi).

Participants – Professors and students at media schools.

Participant selection model - media school professors; Media school students

Target segment - 18-60 years old;

Number of participants - 65 (35 - women; 30 - men);

27 professors (women - 18; men - 9); 38 - students (women - 20; men - 18).

Geography of the study – Tbilisi-Batumi;

Period of research - 2024 – January/February.

The purpose of the study was to identify the challenges of teaching new media and for this purpose we asked the respondents three questions to professors and students.

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Questions for professors (Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University; Caucasus International University; Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University) -

1. To what extent do the teaching methods of your media school correspond to world requirements and the reality of Georgia?
2. What is the role of the multimedia center in the process of training students?
3. What influence did the Soviet past leave on the quality of Georgian media's credibility

The study confirmed that -

- Even more load should be transferred to practical lessons (84%);
- Accordingly, according to 98% of respondents, the role of the multimedia center in the process of studying new media is the most important; გამოკითხულთა უმრავლესობა

- The majority of respondents (73%) believe that traces of the Soviet past still affect the quality of Georgian media's credibility

Questions for students - (Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University; Caucasus International University)

- In your opinion, do you receive education in your media school that corresponds to the world's requirements and the reality of Georgia?
- Is the multimedia center necessary for mastering new media?
- In your opinion, has the Soviet past left an impact on the quality of credibility of the Georgian media?

The study confirmed that -

- According to the majority of students (71%), they receive higher media education appropriate to the times in media schools;
- 95% of respondents consider the existence of a multimedia center as a necessary condition for learning new media;
- A large part of the respondents (52%) believe that the traces of the Soviet past still influence the quality of the credibility of the Georgian media.

In general, the research showed that the complex process of learning new media in modern Georgian media schools is more or less successful. According to the general opinion of students and professors, multimedia centers are of crucial importance in the learning process. For future success, it is necessary to get rid of the Soviet past, which still haunts the modern Georgian media.

Conclusion

In Georgian media schools, the study of new media is conducted thoroughly and in accordance with modern standards. Research has shown that it is time to further strengthen the role of multimedia centers in the process of learning new media, so that along with theoretical education, students can get the practical experience and skills necessary to become professionals. Along with this, the Soviet past of the Georgian media should be understood, re-evaluated, evaluated and analyzed in order to free itself from the Soviet past and earn the credibility of the Georgian "liquid person".

Literature

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